

Technologies for Ocean Sensing project developments in imaging and sensing

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Abstract—The TechOceanS project is developing new remote ocean sensing technology supporting wider ocean measurement and a drive to net zero. The project will deliver 5 new sensor classes for biogeochemistry, biology and ecosystems addressing 10 of 19 EOVs, 31 of 73 subvariables, 6 of 9 MSFD targets together with microplastics and a range of biotoxins and contaminants. It will also develop a new image processing workflow for extracting EOVs (9) and MSFD (6) and litter measurements from images. These innovations concentrate on key capability gaps in ocean observing from non-ship systems with a focus on low-cost per measurement through minimised instrument and deployment costs. This paper gives a brief overview of the technologies, and where possible, because of progress or protection of intellectual property, details of our approaches and early results.

Keywords—Sensors; Samplers; Imaging; Essential Ocean Variables; Nutrients; Ocean Carbonate System; Organic Pollution; Primary Production; eDNA; Microorganisms; Phytoplankton; Plastic particles; Plastic Pollution; Ecosystem Characterisation; Machine Learning; Feature Extraction; Microsensors; Recombinant Antibodies; Immunosensors; isothermal amplification; in situ; assays; Microfluidic; Lab on chip; Time resolved fluorescence

I. INTRODUCTION

The TechOceanS project is developing a wide portfolio of technologies that address current gaps in capability to remotely measure Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) as well as regulatory targets such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive and OSPAR. Such measurements have wide application in ocean science, sustainable responses to climate change, food production, and human health. TechOceans principally develops sensor, sampler and image processing technologies where current systems are not able to make measurements from unattended moorings or from small autonomous vehicles, or where the current paradigm is for manual sampling and later laboratory analysis. Filling such gaps not only increases capability, it enables smaller and less carbon intensive observing platforms: a key enabler in the transition to net zero ocean observing capability.

This paper prioritises an overview of the novel measurement technologies being developed, and gives detail, where possible, of recent design development and test results.

II. OCEAN DEPLOYABLE CYTOMETER FOR THE ANALYSIS OF PHYTOPLANKTON AND MICROPLASTICS

A. Introduction

Phytoplankton are responsible for up to 50% of primary production globally [4] and so it is vital that the health, composition and quantity of phytoplankton communities are monitored to assess the state of the ocean ecosystem especially in response to anthropogenic effects [5, 6]. Microplastic pollution in the ocean is a growing problem, with few techniques available to monitor levels especially for the smallest size fraction of particles [7].

Flow cytometers can be used to analyse phytoplankton and microplastics. They operate by flowing seawater rapidly through electrical and optical detection apparatus providing information on particle size, internal structure, and species/phenotype. Standard benchtop flow cytometers consist of a delicate assembly of optical, fluidic, and electronic components making them expensive, bulky, and unsuitable for marine deployment. Chip based microcytometers combine microfluidics, microoptics and microelectronics to offer a low cost, robust alternative with increased functionality for deployment in the oceans [8, 9]. Here we present a micro cytometer designed for autonomous deployment in the ocean which uses impedance and fluorescence measurements to size, discriminate and quantify microplastics and phytoplankton.

B. Cytometer: Device Design

The cytometer module shown in Figure 1 is designed to be deployable to a depth of 2000m. It consists of a pressure balanced compartment containing the chip and a pressure sealed compartment containing the fluorescence pick-up optics, laser and control electronics. The module will fit within autonomous long-range submarine or surface vessels for multiday deployments. The chip is designed to be semi disposable and consists of a microfluidic channel with

Figure 1 Schematic of the cytometer device design. Showing the internal layout of the deployable module, the chip overview and the sensing mechanism for phytoplankton/microplastics flowing through the microchannel

Figure 2 Analysis of a mixed sample of plankton species and microplastics on the microcytometer. Multiparametric separation of each particle type by (a) Chlorophyll fluorescence signal vs electrical diameter. (b) Phycoerythrin fluorescence signal vs electrical diameter. (c) Phycoerythrin signal vs Chlorophyll signal.

integrated microelectrodes for impedance sensing as well as micro aligned and glued graded index lenses for fluorescence sensing. Seawater is flowed through a microfluidic channel between parallel impedance measurement electrodes to measure the size and electrical properties of a cell/particle. The cell/particle then flows through a spatial fluorescence mask (barcode) and fluorescent light is collected by an on chip graded index (GRIN) lens to measure the pigment content of the cell or intrinsic fluorescence in microplastics.

C. Cytometer: Results and Discussion - Differentiation of microplastics and phytoplankton by size and fluorescence

A mixed lab culture containing *Isocrysis Galbana*, *Rhodomonas sp.* and 5 μm polystyrene microspheres was analysed on the micro cytometer. Figure 2 shows the multiparametric analysis used to separate out individual particles into their nominal groupings. Figure 2 (a) plots chlorophyll signal against electrical diameter. The microplastics and *Isocrysis galbana* (IG) cells are of similar size, around 5 μm in diameter but are separated on this plot as the IG cells exhibit chlorophyll fluorescence while the microplastics do not. *Rhodomonas sp.* is distinguishable as it has both a larger electrical diameter and a larger chlorophyll signal with respect to both IG and the microplastics. Figure 2(b) plots phycoerythrin against electrical diameter. Here the IG and microplastics are not distinguishable as both are of a

similar size and exhibit no phycoerythrin signal. *Rhodomonas* is distinguishable as it exhibits both a strong phycoerythrin signal and is of a larger diameter than the other particle populations. Figure 2 (c) plots the channel 1 chlorophyll signal against the channel 2 phycoerythrin signal. Here all three populations are distinguishable. *Rhodomonas* exhibits both strong chlorophyll and phycoerythrin fluorescence, IG exhibits only chlorophyll fluorescence while the microplastics exhibit no fluorescence. These plots show that the micro cytometer can distinguish between two common marine species and small microplastics. Work will continue to analyse more species of phytoplankton as well as microplastics samples of varying size and material.

A control study was conducted on a standard benchtop flow cytometer (Attune NXT, ThermoFisher, USA) to provide comparative results. Figure 3 shows a two-fluorescence channel histogram of several monodisperse samples overlaid; the small cyanobacteria *Synechococcus* was included in the analysis as a measure for fluorescence from small phytoplankton but these were not measured on the microcytometer. In concurrence with the results gained from the microcytometer, *Rhodomonas* exhibits strong fluorescence on both the chlorophyll and phycoerythrin channels, small co cultured phytoplankton are also observable in this sample which are below the limit of detection for the microcytometer. *Isocrysis galbana* exhibits only chlorophyll

Figure 3 Analysis of monodisperse samples analysed on a benchtop Attune flow cytometer. Traces are overlaid to show the relative signals of each sample.

fluorescence. The 5 μm microspheres do not exhibit strong fluorescence on either channel. These results confirm the accurate performance of the microcytometer for effective discrimination of particle populations.

D. Cytometer: Conclusion

The module design, chip design and sensing mechanism for a deployable cytometer have been demonstrated. The cytometer was successfully used to discriminate two species of marine plankton and a sample of polystyrene microplastics with comparable performance to a benchtop flow cytometer. In future work the microcytometer module will be deployed at the dockside and on autonomous vehicles to demonstrate ocean deployable high-performance cytometry of phytoplankton and microplastics.

E. Cytometer: Methods

Chips were fabricated in a class 100 cleanroom. Two, 700 μm thick BK7 wafers were patterned with the electrode designs of complementary patterns on the base and top wafer. The base wafer was then covered in a SINR dry film photoresist of 40 μm nominal thickness which was patterned by photolithography to produce the micro channels. The final channel height was measured at 35 μm and the microchannel widths of the various chip designs were 60, 80 and 120 μm . The individual 15 x 15 mm chips were diced with a programmable diamond scribe. The electrodes on the top and bottom of the chip were electrically connected by wicking silver epoxy between the layers followed by curing overnight at room temperature. To further seal chip microfluidics flowable epoxy was wicked into the remaining gaps between the wafers and cured for 2 hours at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Inlet and outlet holes were laser milled through the top wafer of each chip using a CO₂ laser cutter.

Bespoke GRIN lenses were obtained from GRINTECH GMBH. The GRIN lenses were designed to be glued directly to the chip aligned directly over the fluorescence analysis region of the microchannel using an infinity focussed camera and micrometre stages. The GRIN lenses were 2 mm in diameter, 4.07 mm long with a pitch of 0.21 and a total

working distance of 718 nm, including 700 μm of BK7 glass and 18 μm of seawater with a numerical aperture (NA) of 0.5, a gradient constant of 0.324 and a maximum and minimum refractive index of 1.596 and 1.516 respectively.

Monocultures of phytoplankton were grown in an incubator at 18 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, under 3000K white LED light at 0.5-2.7 mW/cm² with a day/night cycle of 12/12 hours. Phytoplankton strains and media were obtained from Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa (CCAP) Oban, Scotland, UK. Strains used were: CCAP 211/75 *Chlorella vulgaris*, CCAP 927/1 *Isochrysis galbana*, *Rhodomonas sp.* 5 μm Polystyrene size standard beads were sourced from Merck UK as the microplastics samples.

Plankton and microplastic samples were flowed through the device for analysis at 40 $\mu\text{l}/\text{minute}$. The voltage outputs from the PMT and the current outputs from the impedance electrodes were recorded on a Zurich instruments MFLI lock in amplifier. Analysis of flow cytometry data was performed in Matlab.

III. BIOGEOCHEMICAL MICROSENSORS

TechOceanS has built on the existing and frequently deployed portfolio of *in situ* biogeochemical sensors that use microfluidics [10-17] and are colloquially known as ‘lab on chip’ sensor in the oceanographic community. The principal innovations in TechOceanS is to develop a number of sensors that implement measurement of two or more chemical parameters on a single device.

The sensors are centred on an optofluidic chip to which are attached solenoid valves and stepper motor driven pumps. They drive sample and reagents into the chip which measures the optical response. This architecture can be applied to different analytical chemistry targets with modest design and reagent changes. Many of the reagent chemistries used are based upon gold standard methods enabling metrology provenance, intercomparison and community acceptance. Reagents often include standards and blanks enabling *in situ* calibration. Existing devices are robust, with a depth rating of 6,000 m for most variants.

Figure 4 Graph showing length-normalised absorbance vs nitrate concentration at four different mixing ratios within the Nitrate+Nitrite prototype. The legend indicates the volume ratio of sample:buffer:Griess reagent.

Devices measuring more than one analyte in a single chip include Nitrate+Nitrite, Phosphate+Nitrate, and Silicate+Phosphate, Total Alkalinity+Dissolved Inorganic Carbon. In this new architecture fluidic handling hardware used is also capable of extending the instrument's range: the user can adjust the ratios of sample and reagents used in a spectrophotometric measurement. This enables variation of the degree to which sample (and hence analyte) is diluted by the reagents. This control therefore enables the user to adjust the optical absorbance of a given concentration of sample, or to vary the concentration of a reagent in the analytical procedure. For example, the Nitrate+Nitrite instrument has been tested at temperatures between 5 and 35°C. At room temperature, without substantial optimisation effort, the preliminary limit of detection of the device was 130 nM nitrate, the precision (coefficient of variation of repeat measurements of the same solution in the 0.5-2 µM range) was 1-2%. The effect of sample dilution with reagent, and hence range / sensitivity optimisation in this sensor is visible in the graph depicted in Figure 4.

IV. IMMUNOASSAY MICROSENSORS

The large number of chemicals measured as EOVs, regulatory targets, and for scientific study is a challenge to the global effort to enable measurement of all priority chemicals with sensor enabled autonomy and remote observatories. A principal barrier is the lack of simple or mature analytical chemical assays to access many of these priority chemicals with sufficient limits of detection, and specificity in a format that can be applied for example in an *in situ* analyser (see §III).

Conventional monitoring of environmental contaminants relies on manual sampling and laboratory analysis including complex fluid handling, sub-zero reagents storage capabilities, as well as complex analytical separation systems such as gas chromatography/mass-spectrometry (GC/MS) and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).

To combat this, TechOceanS is developing robust, and *in situ* deployable immunoassays based on recombinant antibodies, and two microfluidic formats (Figure 5) to run these on sensors integrated with ocean observing systems.

Lab-on-Chip technologies are highly customizable and commercially viable alternatives to the current detection methods. As exemplar targets for this approach TechOceanS is focusing on developing robust antibodies-based assays and sensors for the detection of both Harmful Algal Bloom toxins, and emerging contaminants of concern, known to occur in the

Figure 5 Schematic of TechOceanS immunoassay enabled *in situ* sensors. A competitive immunoassay is developed for each target and applied in a Lab On A Disc (LOAD) format (led by DCU) and a linear microfluidic format (led by NOC)

aquatic environment due to anthropogenic inputs, such as diclofenac, bifenthrin and estrone. These targets are selected because of their impact on aquaculture and marine habitats, and because of available immunoassays or suitability for immunoassay development. These targets, assays and their characteristics are listed in table I.

Competitive immunoassays have been developed for the incorporation of multiple immunoassays on either or both a 'Lab On A Disc' (LOAD) format [18], or in a new proprietary linear microfluidic format developed by TechOceanS. Both these formats enable immobilization of target (conjugate) for surface mediated competitive binding assays and the inclusion of reagents within their structure. Parallel channels and sample splitting enable multiplexed detection in both formats.

V. IMAGING AND OPTICS

A. Imaging and Optics: introduction

TechOceanS developments in imaging and optics are focused on 1) methods of image processing, including with Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), to automatically extract information (such as habitat type, or organism taxonomy); 2) evaluate and develop methods for transmitting information extracted from images, over low-bandwidth links, and using this for selected retrieval of (compressed) images; 3) the development and use in ML and AI training of high precision multi-view composite images

TABLE I. IMMUNO ASSAYS DEVELOPED FOR TECHOCEANS

Analytical target	Producer species / Source	Antibody detection	Required limit of detection	EU regulatory limit	References
Hydrophilic harmful algal toxins					
Saxitoxin (STX) (Paralytic shellfish poisoning)	Dinoflagellates (<i>Alexandrium tamarense</i> , <i>Gymnodinium catenatum</i>)	Yes. (LOD 0.03 ng/mL) (available commercially)	Yes. 30 min detection. Au-NPs. LOD 10 fM (3 fg/mL), range 10 fM to 0.1 μ M. ELISA (0.02-0.4 μ g/L)	800 μ g/kg (STX eq.) in shellfish Drinking water 3 μ g/L (GV, guideline value)	EFSA, 2009. WHO, 2020.
Domoic acid (DA) (Amnesic shellfish poisoning)	<i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i>	Yes (available commercially)	Yes (LOD 0.45 ng/mL)	20 mg/kg	EFSA, 2009
Anthropogenic Contaminants					
Diclofenac	Pharmaceutical	LOD 7.8 ng/mL Ic50 44 ng/L ELISA	0.126 μ g/L	0.126 μ g/L (WFD) (10 ng/L EU 2008/105/EC)	Huebner <i>et al.</i> [1]
Bifenthrin	Pharmaceutical	ELISA - IC50 59 ng/mL, LOD 15 ng/mL. GNP-ICS - Visual LOD 50 ng/mL	(ARfD 0.328 mg/kg/day) LD50 mice 43 mg/kg	0.04 μ g/L (WFD)	Yao <i>et al.</i> [2]
Estrone	Not applicable	Yes (commercial kit available)	0.4 ng/L	0.4 ng/L (2008/105/EU)	Glineur <i>et al.</i> [3]

and derived models; 4) hardware and image correction developments for the pelagic particle imaging system UVP6 [19] and a new variant able to characterize smaller particles (UVP6m) as well as connection to an autonomous ocean glider; and development of an *in situ* Phytoplankton Primary Productivity (PhytoPP) sensor using Single Turnover Active Fluorometry (STAF). Recent result for each are presented briefly below.

B. Imaging and Optics: Image processing

For both the pelagic (e.g. UVP6), and benthic (e.g. BIOCAM [20]) images we have addressed AI and ML techniques for compression and extraction of information such as habitat type, or organism taxonomy. In ML and AI training for both applications, we have compared the following approaches:

supervised (i.e. application of human expert knowledge through annotated training data, manual tuning of parameters / feature engineering)

Figure 6 Schematic of colour, scale, and distortion normalisation with example illustrative images

Figure 7 Bathymetric charts (see greyscale legend) for the Studland Bay area (Dorset, UK) with overlaid habitat type classification pseudolabels (see colour legend). The location of 'Eco-moorings' is shown by red lined yellow filled diamonds in the left chart.

unsupervised (no human input into information extraction – i.e. use of autoencoders)

semi supervised (unsupervised identification of a small subset of representative images that are annotated by humans to create a labelled data subset that is then used to classify unlabeled data (creating pseudo-labelled data) and the results of the human and machine classification combined to improve the model).

In both applications we have also investigated the improvement in the unsupervised autoencoders using meta-data, such as geographical location, or depth.

1) Pelagic Agnostic AI

For pelagic (e.g. UVP6) images the workflow used latent (autoencoded) representation encoding with and without meta data, so that the effect of adding the latter could be analysed. This was followed by unsupervised clustering and semi-supervised training including using multiple views of the same object (hereafter 'multi-view'). The two-step multi-view classification was used to reduce the effect of detritus and apply balanced supervision of views.

Using the widely used in machine learning F1 score (a measure of predictive skill based on precision and recall) the results demonstrated that compared to the Naïve classification (F1 = 0.33), incorporation of depth metadata (F1 = 0.53) and then also multi-view class (F1 = 0.55) improved the performance of the classification.

Figure 8 Computer-generated image from a 3D model of a *Praunus Flexuosus* specimen scanned in the lab

Figure 9 3D CAD rendered image of the UVP6m benchtop prototype

2) Benthic image formation models

Recent work has used metadata based image formation models to correct, crop, resample and undistort images prior to autoencoding and semi-supervised learning. An illustrative schematic of this technique is shown in Figure 6. Image translation can include compensation for the known or estimated water column properties such as wavelength depended transmission, absorption and scatter. As shown in Figure 6 the application of corrections improved image quality with increasing fidelity of depth representation and hence water column optical effects on an image colour. In the far left column we can see the optimal image is obtained by correcting for water column optical properties with a pixel by pixel depth map. Whilst a uniform colour correct (without depth information, image second column from left) and a correction using the mean altitude / depth (column second from right) improve the image, this is inferior to using a depth map.

One of the advantages of the application of an image formation model is that it creates images that are largely independent of the sensor / imaging system used to acquire them, and are more resilient to changes to watercolumn condition variability. This is advantageous in generating training, validation and operational datasets for AI / ML image processing. We have recently explored the robustness of this technique, and the ability of the encoding to be sensor agnostic [21].

Figure 10 Composite image and schematic showing images of UVP6 integrated with Seaglider and Slocum G3 ocean gliders (left) and overview schematic of SIRMA™ location in a wider data system and principal functional blocks. © Ehsan Abdi (Cyprus Subsea)

C. Imaging and Optics: Image information transmission of low-bandwidth

With increasing energy specific computing power, it is now possible to use autoencoding in situ and at near real-time to enable transmission of information from image-based surveys from the remote ocean. During the project we plan to demonstrate this workflow, including the autoencoder guided operator selection of priority images for communication over low-bandwidth. To date we have demonstrated the ability of autoencoders to process the data offline. An example dataset is shown in Figure 7. Here the encoders exhibited excellent skill to separate Rock / Algae ($F1 = 0.96$), Sand ($F1 = 0.71$) and Seagrass ($F1=0.91$), and had moderate to good skill ($F1 = 0.23$ to 0.60) for categorising Seagrass habitats into bands with a range or coverage of 20% in each band. This excellent performance shows that information can be extracted from data dense images into a low data size format that retains the critical information (in this case the Essential Ocean Variable, Seagrass Cover by location) and is suitable for transmission over low-bandwidth links.

D. Imaging and Optics: Multi-view images and models for image processing

One of the principal challenges for the use of AI and ML for taxonomy of organisms is the generation, or acquisition of high-quality training sets. This is particularly acute in the pelagic phase and for microorganisms where species, and sometimes species from a different genus can be morphological and hence optically similar. This frequently requires laborious image analysis by highly trained taxonomists, who nonetheless are not immune to error, and may necessitate laborious confirmatory analysis (e.g. by genotyping). To address this hurdle to AI / ML assisted taxonomy TechOceanS has mined and contributed to existing datasets of gold standard labelled images as per the current paradigm. However, in addition we have investigated the automated generation of high-quality microorganism images from laboratory (and therefore known species) specimens.

Since lab images differ significantly from in-situ appearance in the ocean, we create a sensor-agnostic 3D

computer graphics model from the lab images for each specimen. Such a model can then be used to artificially create additional images of the specimen in different waters or for different camera sensors. For obtaining such a model (visual 3D reconstruction) of small samples however, limited depth-of field is a challenge and we have designed a novel procedure for calibration of macro lenses for photogrammetric scenarios as well as a mathematical camera model for focus stacking [22]. An example, synthetic rendering of a scanned plankton object is displayed in Figure 8.

E. Imaging and Optics: UVP6 and UVP6m and integration on gliders with SIRMA™¹

The UVP6 is a quantitative imaging sensor used to monitor large particulate matter ($100\text{--}2000\ \mu\text{m}$) and plankton. Its low power requirement, small size and low imaging frequency enable it to be deployed on marine autonomous platforms.

In addition to the use of UVP6 in the acquisition of images for AI / ML taxonomy TechOceanS has enabled further development of the optical design / hardware and development of a variant for smaller particles – the UVP6m. This reduced the minimum size for particle detection to $10\ \mu\text{m}$ and for $100\ \mu\text{m}$ for classification. A 3D CAD rendered image of the benchtop prototype UVP6m is shown in Figure 9. An *in situ* prototype is in development and will be deployed during the project.

In addition, integration of the sensor with two types of ocean glider has been undertaken using SIRMA™¹. This is a smart device that transforms a conventional cable assembly into an intelligent processing unit, by incorporating a low-power modular printed circuit board inline between a sensor and platform. This innovative assembly enables various functions, including data processing, data logging, and voltage regulation, for a seamless communication between a sensor and a platform such as a glider, AUV, or buoy. SIRMA™ has been used for the integration of the

¹ trademark held by Cyprus Subsea Consulting and Services C.S.C.S. Ltd.

Figure 11 3D CAD rendering and image composite of MicroSTAF - an in situ Phytoplankton Primary Productivity sensor. Sensor internals and connection to external contextual sensors (top), detail of optical head internal (bottom left) and overview of external appearance and key characteristics (bottom right)

Underwater Vision Profiler 6 (UVP6) to gliders. A schematic of this system is shown on the RHS of Figure 10

The UVP6 was integrated on two different gliders, the Seaglider (M1, Huntington Ingalls Industries; operated by Cyprus Subsea Consulting and Services C.S.C.S. Ltd) and Slocum G3 using SIRMA™ technology (see Figure 10). SIRMA™ facilitated the communication between the gliders and UVP6 by receiving information about the state of the glider and making decisions accordingly to alter the sampling parameters for UVP6. Onboard image processing by the UVP6, includes picking objects from the background of images, characterizing and counting different particle sizes and abundance in different depth zones (Picheral et al. 2021). SIRMA™ records UVP6 output and sends a standardized subset of data to glider for transmission to shore.

Seaglider-UVP6 missions using SIRMA™ technology were launched to study the Polar front area two consecutive years (April 2021 and April 2022) and the continental margin north and west of Svalbard in October 2022. Slocum-UVP6 missions using SIRMA™ technology are planned to be launched in the Norwegian Sea in May 2023. The recorded data is available on EcoTaxa (obs-vlfr.fr).

In a similar way SIRMA™ technology can be used to integrate new sensors to gliders and other platforms taking advantage of the facilitated power connection, in-situ data relay and data standardization.

F. Imaging and Optics: in situ STAF sensor development

PhytoPP is a critical metric for ocean and Earth science, and for study of climate change as it describes how much carbon is fixed by planktonic photosynthetic activity. It is therefore, a master variable of the ocean biological carbon pump the characterisation of which is critical to understanding and quantifying ocean carbon dioxide sequestration.

Nonetheless, PhytoPP is not a principal Essential Ocean Variable, partly due to difficulty in accurate measurement, particularly at Sea. Instead it is a sub-variable of the EOVS 'Phytoplankton biomass and diversity'. TechOceanS is developing optical technology to address the difficulty of measuring PhytoPP at Sea, and particularly from small autonomous vehicles.

Following the successful demonstration of the Single Turnover Active Fluorometry (STAF) principle [23] and introduction of the laboratory-based product 'LabSTAF' (Chelsea Technologies Group, UK), a first in situ prototype 'AutoSTAF' was developed for the UK Oceanids project [24]. TechOceanS has enabled the development of an improved in situ prototype 'MicroSTAF' with lower power (80% reduction to $< 2\text{ W}$), a 72% decrease in volume and increased pressure rating from 600 to 2000 m. A 3D CAD rendering giving an overview of the MicroSTAF instrument, its principal elements and specification is shown Figure 11.

VI. PARTICLE AND eDNA SAMPLER AND GENOMIC SENSOR

TechOceanS is introducing new processes and technologies which allow eDNA to be collected and sequenced continuously and in highly challenging subaquatic environments. This includes:

- the development of two sampler technologies, both developed for eDNA and microorganism analysis, but also being developed within TechOceanS to filter collect and preserve microplastics.
- The development of a sensor for the quantification of DNA and RNA

A. Particle, eDNA and microorganism samplers

Of the two sampler technologies, the most robust is the Robotic Cartridge Sampling Instrument (RoCSI) which is recently commercially available from McLane Research Laboratories inc, USA [25]. This device has been optimised and improved from an existing design within TechOceanS having been developed in a number of projects including AtlantOS (EU), iAtlantic (EU) [26-28] and MARINe-DNA (NERC). It samples user specified volumes of sample (seawater) through filter cartridges (Sterivex, Merk(Millipore), Germany) followed by a preservative solution before indexing to a fresh cartridge. The second sampler design developed in TechOceanS uses a continuous ribbon of filter material which is similarly sequentially indexed over a pumping manifold and preservative flush station. This arrangement has minimal contamination from sampler materials or moving parts and has been evaluated for use as a microplastics as well as eDNA and microorganism sampler.

B. Nucleic Acid Sensor

The in situ nucleic acid sensor utilises molecular assays that include an amplification step. The technology is currently at TRL4 with separate modules evaluated in the lab for: sample filtration, capture and lysis; nucleic acid extraction and purification; and multiplexed amplification and detection.

Module 1 draws upon the developments of the sampler technologies described above. Subsequent modules uses a proprietary linear microfluidic technology similar to that used for the immunoassay sensors (see §IV). TechOceanS has developed over ten new isothermal assays for the identification of key target species that can be applied using this technology.

Preconcentration of nucleic acid (module 2) from the initial sample is critical to efficient downstream amplification and detection. This process includes binding of nucleic acid in lysate on a solid substrate, washing to remove cells debris and elution of DNA for amplification. For a simple fluidic system to be operated on an in situ analyzer, we selected DNA-binding magnetic beads to concentrate the DNA, as this does not require pressure to push sample through a silica membrane. Lysis of cells and binding of DNA to a solid surface requires a chaotropic agent and the presence of salts, respectively. To eliminate the need to carry ready-made lysis reagents on the analyzer, we developed a concept where the seawater sample (residual water after filtration) resuspends a pre-weighed amount of guanidine hydrochloride powder in module 1. Therefore, the seawater sample containing the target cells is transformed into a lysis buffer. We initially

Figure 12 Bar Graph showing comparison of LAMP amplification of *Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata* DNA extracts using Qiagen's DNeasy Plant mini kit, versus the developed protocol with magnetic beads. Vertical bars indicate standard deviation from replicate samples

tested for the optimal type of chaotropic reagent (guanidine hydrochloride vs thiocyanate), and the optimal washing reagents (ethanol versus isopropanol). We also tested whether heating or agitating the sample during lysis significantly improved the yield. As the presence of debris in the sample meant we could not quantify the preconcentrated DNA by optical methods, we used an isothermal quantitative colorimetric LAMP assay (reported elsewhere) and measured the time to detect the amplification signal. The final protocol included guanidine hydrochloride added to 1 ml of seawater and to a final concentration of 4 M, incubation for 5 mins without heat or agitation, capture of DNA using MagneSil DNA-binding beads (Promega, UK), a wash with isopropanol and elution in water. The performance of this protocol was evaluated on a cultured isolate of the toxic diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata* isolated from Napoli, Italy, against a standard laboratory DNA extraction using the DNeasy mini kit (QIAGEN, USA). The performance of the two approaches was found to be similar (see Figure 12).

VII. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The TechOceanS project is developing sensor and sampler technologies that address current gaps in global capability to measure and sample key EOVs and regulatory targets from unattended moorings or from small autonomous vehicles. Filling such gaps not only increases capability (such as increasing data density in both space and time for target parameters), it enables cost and carbon emissions reduction by enabling smaller platforms and reducing the need for carbon intensive ship or personnel visits.

The technologies developed have been selected based on a combination of: the priority that the global ocean observation community have ascribed to the parameter; the technological opportunity to address the gap; the extent to which the technology can address multiple parameters / measurement targets; and the cost and carbon emissions savings that are possible with each technology developed.

The project has therefore prioritised Biological and Biogeochemical variables where the biggest gaps in capability remain. The Cytometer device measures phytoplankton biomass (enumerating populations and measuring individual's volume) and provides information on diversity through taxonomic discrimination. It also enumerates and measures volumes of micro / nano plastics as

well as small particulate matter. The Biogeochemical Microsensors so far developed target the priority parameters nutrients and inorganic carbon. Immunoassay Microsensors currently target priority and emerging water contaminants as well as toxigenic phytoplankton / their toxins (MSFD and OSPAR targets). Benthic image processing addresses 'cover and composition' EOVs, such as 'Seagrass cover and composition' as well as benthic fauna / invertebrate abundance and distribution. Pelagic imaging targets fish abundance and distribution, larger phytoplankton as well as zooplankton biomass and diversity EOVs. Marine litter can also be quantified in benthic and pelagic images. Image formation models and image information transmission aid the efficiency of these image processing workflows. The in situ STAF sensor targets Phytoplankton Primary Productivity – the basis of all oceanic biological activity, as well as providing further information on phytoplankton and microbe biomass and diversity. Finally, ecogenomic sensing and sampling addresses at least in part, all biology and ecosystem EOVs, through quantification of eDNA or direct measurement of microbial nucleic acids. The sampling elements of these systems are also being adapted to enable collection and study of microplastics.

Whilst the primary aim of TechOceanS is the development of biogeochemical and biology and ecosystem observation capability a further aim is to develop and demonstrate how the combination of these new measurements, and also combination with existing (e.g. physical EOV) sensors can provide new insights on interactions and feedbacks within and between ocean physics, chemistry and biology.

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